

Frequency-Domain RF Self-Interference Cancellation for In-Band Full-Duplex Communications

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Abstract—Wireless backhaul has recently gained a significant amount of interest as a cost-effective solution in comparison with conventional backhaul technologies with dedicated microwave links or fiber optics. Self-interference cancellation (SIC) is an enabling technology that allows wireless backhaul to operate in the more spectrum-efficient in-band full-duplex (IBFD) operation mode instead of the out-of-band mode. Compared to Wi-Fi IBFD transceivers, wireless in-band backhaul systems face some unique challenges, such as significantly higher transmission power and much larger propagation delay spread for the self-interference signal, especially in the low-frequency bands under 1 GHz, which often prevent accurate SIC performance. The SIC is often implemented with an interference-cancelling filter, where the filter weights are essentially the channel estimates of the self-interference signals. In this paper, a frequency-domain Radio Frequency (RF) SIC (RF-SIC) framework with a novel filter weight optimization algorithm is proposed to tackle the challenges of wireless in-band backhaul. The proposed RF-SIC does not require a dedicated training phase which needs to stop the transmission of the backhaul signal. Moreover, it has the capability of tracking the self-interference channel variation since the filter weights are updated in a block-by-block fashion.

Index Terms—In-band full-duplex, self-interference cancellation, wireless backhaul, adaptive filter.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the explosive increase of demands for data throughput on the limited wireless spectrum, innovation in spectrum-efficient technologies is needed more than ever. Among the

This work was funded by the Communications Research Centre, part of the Department of Innovation, Science and Economic Development Canada, and the Institute of Information & Communications Technology Planning & Evaluation (IITP) grant funded by the Korean government (MSIT) (No. 2017-0-00081, Development of Transmission Technology for Ultra High Quality (UHQ) UHD). This work was also co-funded by the Basque Government (under the grant IT1436-22 and the grant Elkartek KK-2022/00069) and by the Spanish Government under the grant PID2021-124706OB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF A way of making Europe.

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Part of this work was published at IEEE BMSB 2022.

various spectrum efficient technologies, in-band full-duplex (IBFD) communication, where a wireless device transmits and receives signals at the same time in the same frequency band, has attracted significant attentions [1]–[7]. Compared to traditional half-duplex communications, IBFD can double the spectrum efficiency of the point-to-point link. Moreover, IBFD has the potential to significantly increase the overall throughput of a wireless network due to the removal of the constraints on self-collision [1]. More recently, wireless backhaul with IBFD has been investigated for 3GPP Integrated Access and Backhaul (IAB) for 5G with the benefit of significant infrastructure cost reduction [8]–[10]. A wireless in-band backhaul technology was also proposed for the next generation of TV broadcasting with Single Frequency Networks (SFN) [11].

In IBFD communications, self-interference (SI) due to the loopback signal (LBS) from the co-located transmitter is the main challenge, as the power of SI is significantly stronger than the desired received signals from the remote transmitter. In essence, SI cancellation (SIC) techniques try to reconstruct the SI and subtract it from the received signal to achieve a desirable signal-to-interference-plus-noise (SINR) level for the signal of interest. Since SI is simply the LBS attenuated by the loopback channel, reconstructing the SI depends on the availability of the loopback channel’s channel state information (CSI) and a copy of the LBS [12]. SIC techniques generally can be characterized in propagation domain [13], analog/Radio Frequency (RF) domain [14]–[17], and baseband/digital domain [2]–[5].

For analog/RF domain SIC, LBS can be obtained by tapping the signal after the transmitter chain’s power amplifier (PA) or at the transmit antenna waveguide and fed to the receiver through a cable as a reference signal (RS). After CSI is obtained at the receiver, filter weights can be derived and applied to the RS either in the time domain (TD) or frequency domain for the SI reconstruction.

Depending on how CSI is acquired at the receiver, there are training-based SIC and non-training-based SIC approaches. In [18], a training-based SI cancellation used a training phase to obtain the adaptive filter weights, which are the loopback channel estimates. Then during the data transmission phase, the filter weights are applied to the reference signal to reconstruct the LBS to be cancelled out from the received signal.

A training-based SIC was proposed in [19] where the channel estimation is performed at baseband during the training phase. Then these channel estimates are applied in both the RF cancellation and the baseband digital cancellation stages. In [20], a training-based cascade SIC scheme for Multi-Input Multi-Output (MIMO) frequency-domain transceiver was proposed, which exploits a close relationship between the self-talk and cross-talk channels in the MIMO WiFi receivers.

In contrast to the aforementioned training-based SIC techniques, several blind methods were proposed for SIC in the literature, where blind is in the sense of no *a priori* CSI of the loopback channel at the receiver and no training phase is provided for the receiver to acquire the CSI. Blind SIC foregoes the need for the training phase, therefore, it is more bandwidth efficient. A blind analog SIC was proposed in [21] based on the carrier recovery techniques for BPSK signals, thus limiting its application to BPSK signals only. An approach based on Blind Known SI Cancellation (BKSC) was proposed in [22] that combines the received signal and its weighted off-shifted version to cancel the SI, therefore no CSI is required. If the SI channel is frequency selective, the same process is repeated L times for successive SI cancellation, where L is the number of multipaths. In [22], performance for SI channel with 2-path was presented with notable degradation compared to the bound. For SI channels with much a larger delay spread and more multipaths, the performance of BKSC is questionable. SIC based on blind source separation (BSS) for IBFD was proposed in [12]. Although there is a “blind” in the name of this approach, it requires the SI channel estimates through training. A blind SIC was proposed in [23] based on the known autocorrelation of the cyclic prefix in OFDM systems. A blind time-domain adaptive SI cancellation scheme was proposed in [24] for full-duplex MIMO relays. It is worth pointing out that adaptive filter approaches can be applied in SIC, although these techniques were not called “blind” approaches, they don’t require dedicated training phase/training sequences in the tuning process, e.g [25], [26].

The analog/RF domain SIC can be implemented either in time-domain (TD) or frequency-domain, see [6] and references therein. In the time-domain implementation, the SIC is realized with a multiple taps filter where each tap has a fixed delay and adjustable phase and amplitude control. A SIC based on frequency-domain equalization approach was proposed in [27]. The significant advantage of frequency-domain approaches over time-domain cancellation is that the delay elements within each tap are eliminated, which greatly simplifies integrated circuit implementations [5], this is particularly true for the scenarios where the SI channel exhibits a very large delay spread, which can be as much as several tens of micro-seconds [28]. The large delay spread of the SI channel is due to long multipath reflections on the UHF band or under SFN operation, where several transmitters emit the same RF signal to increase coverage areas [29].

Above mentioned analog/RF domain SIC techniques are mostly designed for the WiFi or LTE small cell transceivers. For wireless in-band backhaul, especially for broadcast systems, there are unique challenges, including high power, low antenna directivity, and large delay spread for the SI channel.

To the best knowledge of the authors, there is no analog/RF domain SIC designed to address these issues, especially the large delay spread, in the literature.

The contributions of this paper are as follows: 1) A frequency-domain RF-SIC framework is proposed with a novel filter weight optimization based on DFT-windowing, where either the over-the-air RF reference signal (OTA-RFRS) or the direct RF reference signal (D-RFRS) can be used. 2) Based on the same principle of the frequency-domain RF-SIC, a frequency-domain MIMO RF-SIC (MIMO-RFSIC) framework is proposed, where either the OTA-RFRS or the D-RFRS can be used. 3) When D-RFRS is used, a special case of low complexity frequency-domain MIMO-RFSIC is proposed where the RF-SIC can be performed at each received antenna chain separately. The proposed schemes forego the training phase and training sequence to acquire the filter weights. The proposed schemes require only one FFT block to achieve the near-optimal filter weights with affordable complexity. Moreover, the proposed schemes can effectively cancel the SI even when the SI channel exhibits a very large delay spread.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the RF-SIC with two different RF reference signals (RFRS). Optimal SIC filter weights are analyzed and a frequency-domain RF-SIC framework is presented in Section III. In Section IV, the frequency-domain MIMO-RFSIC is presented, with a special case of low complexity implementation. Simulation results are presented in Section V. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section VI.

The following notations are used throughout the paper. We use lower-case letters for time domain scalars, capital letters for frequency-domain scalars, boldface capital letters for vectors or matrices, $\{A_k\}$ to denote a vector with elements A_k , $\{A_{ij}\}$ to denote a matrix with elements A_{ij} , $\{\mathbf{A}_k\}$ to denote a matrix vector with matrices elements \mathbf{A}_k , $*$ for conjugate, $\mathcal{E}[\cdot]$ for expectation over all the FFT bins, and $\mathcal{D}[\cdot]$ to denote the DFT windowing process.

II. RF SELF-INTERFERENCE CANCELLATION

The essence of self-interference cancellation is to reconstruct the interference signal and subtract it from the received signal, such that the interference-free desired signal can be further processed with channel estimation, demodulation and decoding. The gap between the power of SI and the desired signal is about 0 ~ 100 dB depending on the transmit/receive antenna separation and isolation [30]. Due to the dynamic range limit of the analog-to-digital conversion (ADC) unit, it is desirable to use a two-stage SIC with analog/RF cancellation followed by digital cancellation. In this paper, we focus on RF cancellation.

Successfully reconstructing the SI in SIC relies on both the CSI of the SI or loopback channels and the reference signals. Due to the hardware imperfection, the SI signals always contain nonlinear distortion from the high power amplifier (HPA) and other circuitry elements [31]. Moreover, the SI may also contain adjacent channel interference (ACI) as in the

ATSC 3.0¹ transmitter where multiple channels of programs are transmitted at the same time. An RF reference signal, which contains both the same nonlinear distortion and ACI as the SI signal, can lead to a simpler RF SIC design.

A schematic illustration of an IBFD transceiver with two different kinds of RFRS for a Single-Input Single-Output (SISO) system is shown in Fig. 1, where the main receive antenna Rx receives the desired signals from the remote transmitter and the self-interference signals from the co-located transmit antenna Tx. Separating the Rx and Tx antennas can effectively reduce the SI power. Such practice is suitable for wireless backhaul with less real estate constraint, especially for broadcasting systems like ATSC 3.0, where the transmit antenna is mounted at the top of a high tower.

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of an IBFD transceiver block diagram for a SISO system. Either D-RFRS or OTA-RFRS is used for the proposed RF-SIC.

A. Direct RF Reference Signal

The reference signal is obtained by tapping at the transmitter antenna waveguide and fed to the receiver through cable. This is called the direct RF reference signal. Since D-RFRS and SI signals share the same RF chain, they both have the same nonlinear distortion and ACI from the co-located transmitter. This D-RFRS is modelled as the transmitted signal attenuated by a single tap of fixed gain and delay.

B. Over-the-Air RF Reference Signal

In Fig. 1, a separated antenna RS-Rx is used to receive the signal transmitted from the co-located transmit antenna Tx to provide a reference signal to the receiver, therefore, this reference signal is called over-the-air RF reference signal (OTA-RFRS) [33]. The RS-Rx antenna is placed close to the Rx antenna and can be realized with an antenna array with beamforming to the co-located Tx. OTA-RFRS and SI signals share the same transmitter chain and similar surrounding propagation environment. Therefore, OTA-RFRS and SI signals have the same nonlinear distortion and ACI from both the co-located transmitter and neighbour transmitters.

¹Advanced Television Systems Committee (ATSC) is a Washington DC-based international standard body on terrestrial digital TV standard development. ATSC 3.0 is the next-generation TV (NexGenTV) standard that is currently being deployed in the US, South Korea, Jamaica, and is being considered for adoption in many other countries. The system is designed for the UHF band operation using OFDM modulation, LDPC code, and power-based non-orthogonal multiplexing (P-NOM) [32].

III. A FREQUENCY-DOMAIN RF-SIC FRAMEWORK

For an OFDM system, the frequency-domain RF-SIC is operated on each OFDM symbol. For a non-OFDM system, the frequency-domain RF-SIC is operated on each block of N_F samples, where N_F is the size of FFT. The received signal and the RFRS are converted to the frequency domain by FFT. The RFRS is then multiplied with a weight at each FFT bin and subtracted from the received signal. The output signal is then converted back to the time domain by IFFT for further processing. Obviously, the proposed frequency-domain SIC is performed in digital format, therefore, it is different from the conventional analog-domain SIC (A-SIC). However, to differentiate from the second stage digital/baseband cancellation, we will call the proposed schemes RF-SIC as the reference signal comes from an RF signal.

Let Y_k denote the received signal at the receive antenna Rx at the k -th FFT bin. In contrast to the LBS, the desired signal from the remote transmitter is called forward signal (FWS). At the k -th FFT bin, let F_k denote the FWS channel frequency-domain response between the remote transmit antenna and the receive antenna Rx, S_k denote the FWS, X_k denote the LBS, and B_k denote the loopback channel frequency-domain response between the co-located Tx and Rx. The received signal Y_k can be written as:

$$Y_k = F_k S_k + \sqrt{\kappa_Y} B_k X_k + Z_{Y,k} \quad (1)$$

where $Z_{Y,k}$ is the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with zero mean and variance σ^2 , κ_Y is the average power ratio between LBS and FWS.

Similarly, let H_k denote the FWS channel frequency-domain response between the remote transmit antenna and the receive antenna RS-Rx, and A_k denote the loopback channel frequency-domain response between the co-located Tx and RS-Rx. The RF reference signal received at RS-Rx, R_k , can be written as

$$R_k = \sqrt{\rho} H_k S_k + \sqrt{\kappa_R} A_k X_k + Z_{R,k} \quad (2)$$

where $Z_{R,k}$ is the AWGN with zero mean and variance σ^2 , ρ represents the average power ratio of the FWS in Y_k and R_k , and κ_R is the average power of the LBS. For D-RFRS, ρ is zero since no FWS is presented. Without loss of generality, it is assumed that the average powers of signals S_k and X_k are 1, and the channel gains are also normalized to be 1, such that $\mathcal{E}[|F_k|^2] = \mathcal{E}[|B_k|^2] = \mathcal{E}[|H_k|^2] = \mathcal{E}[|A_k|^2] = 1$, where $\mathcal{E}[\cdot]$ is the expectation over N_F FFT bins.

Let $\{W_k\}$ be the weights applied to the RFRS for reconstructing the SI signal to be subtracted from the received signal. The output of the RF-SIC can be written as

$$E_k = Y_k - W_k R_k \quad (3)$$

In a training-based SIC, there is no data transmission from the remote transmitter during the training phase, the co-located transmitter transmits known sequences to the receiver for loopback channel estimation. The received signal in (1) becomes

$$Y_k = \sqrt{\kappa_Y} B_k X_k + Z_{Y,k} \quad (4)$$

and the reference signal in (2) becomes $R_k = X_k$. The conventional training-based SIC techniques developed for (4) are not applicable for the signal models in (1) and (2).

A. Filter Weights for Ideal SI Cancellation

As our objective is to cancel the SI from Y_k in (1), examining the error signal by substituting (1), (2) into (3), we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned} E_k &= (F_k - \sqrt{\rho}W_k H_k)S_k \\ &+ (\sqrt{\kappa_Y}B_k - W_k \sqrt{\kappa_R}A_k)X_k + Z_{E,k} \\ &= \mathcal{S}(S_k) + \mathcal{I}(X_k) + Z_{E,k} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $Z_{E,k} = Z_{Y,k} - W_k Z_{R,k}$, $\mathcal{S}(S_k)$ and $\mathcal{I}(X_k)$ represent the desired signal term and the residual SI term. The FWS SINR can be expressed as

$$\text{SINR} = \frac{\mathcal{E}[|\mathcal{S}(S_k)|^2]}{\mathcal{E}[|\mathcal{I}(X_k) + Z_{E,k}|^2]} \quad (6)$$

Easy to see that ideal SI cancellation is achieved when the residual SI term $\mathcal{I}(X_k)$ becomes zero. Therefore, the filter weights for ideal SI cancellation can be written as

$$W_{opt,k} = \arg \min_W |\mathcal{I}(X_k)|^2 = \frac{\sqrt{\kappa_Y/\kappa_R}B_k}{A_k} \quad (7)$$

If the pure transmitted signal X_k is used as reference signal, $R_k = X_k$, Eq. (7) reduces to $W_{opt,k} = \sqrt{\kappa_Y}B_k$, which is the loopback channel gain. In practice, there is always attenuation on the RF reference signal, therefore, $W_{opt,k}$ is the ‘‘gain’’ of the RFRS at the loopback channel.

Although our ultimate goal is to maximize the FWS SINR, we argue that such a goal can be achieved when the residual SI is minimized without reducing the power of the desired signal $\mathcal{S}(S_k)$. Indeed such argument is true when ρ is zero in (5), the maximum SINR is $1/(1 + \kappa_Y/\kappa_R)\sigma^2$. When using OTA-RFRS, $\rho \neq 0$, substituting (7) into (5), the output signal can be written as

$$E_k = (F_k - \sqrt{\rho}W_{opt,k}H_k)S_k + Z_{E,k} \quad (8)$$

The SINR of the desired FWS can then be derived as

$$\text{SINR} = \frac{\mathcal{E}[|(F_k - \sqrt{\rho}W_{opt,k}H_k)S_k|^2]}{\sigma_{Z_E}^2} \quad (9)$$

where $\sigma_{Z_E}^2$ is the variance of $Z_{E,k}$.

In practice, the Rx antenna may be realized with a directional antenna pointing to the remote transmitter, while the RS-Rx antenna may be realized with another directional antenna pointing to the co-located transmitter. In such a set-up, ρ can be very small, $\rho \ll 1$. Therefore, the SINR in (9) can be rewritten as

$$\text{SINR} \approx \frac{\mathcal{E}[|F_k S_k|^2]}{\sigma_{Z_E}^2} = \frac{1}{(1 + \kappa_Y/\kappa_R)\sigma^2} \quad (10)$$

which is the same as that of $\rho = 0$. Therefore, we claim that the filter weights for ideal SI cancellation can also achieve maximum FWS SINR. Without causing ambiguity, the filter weights $W_{opt,k}$ will be referred to as the optimal filter weights in this paper.

Eq. (10) also indicates that the noise floor increases by a factor of $(1 + \kappa_Y/\kappa_R)$ due to the introduction of the filtered reference signal.

B. Filter Weights for Minimum Mean Square Error

Let $W_{L,k}$ denote the filter weights that achieve minimum mean square error (MSE), $\mathcal{E}|E_k|^2$, at the current FFT block. Without loss of generality, $W_{L,k}$ can be written as

$$W_{L,k} = W_{opt,k} + W_{E,k} \quad (11)$$

where W_{opt} is from (7), then $W_{E,k}$ is the difference between $W_{L,k}$ and $W_{opt,k}$. Substituting (11) into (5), the error signal can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} E_k &= (F_k - \sqrt{\rho}W_{L,k}H_k)S_k \\ &+ (\sqrt{\kappa_Y}B_k - W_{L,k}\sqrt{\kappa_R}A_k)X_k + Z_{E,k} \\ &= (F_k - \sqrt{\rho}W_{L,k}H_k)S_k \\ &\quad - \sqrt{\kappa_R}W_{E,k}A_k X_k + Z_{Y,k} - W_{L,k}Z_{R,k} \\ &= (F_k - \sqrt{\rho}W_{opt,k}H_k)S_k \\ &\quad - W_{E,k}(\sqrt{\rho}H_k S_k + \sqrt{\kappa_R}A_k X_k + Z_{R,k}) \\ &\quad + Z_{Y,k} - W_{opt,k}Z_{R,k} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

To minimize the MSE, $E_k = 0$, we have

$$W_{E,k} = \frac{(F_k - \sqrt{\rho}W_{opt,k}H_k)S_k + Z_{Y,k} - W_{opt,k}Z_{R,k}}{\sqrt{\rho}H_k S_k + \sqrt{\kappa_R}A_k X_k + Z_{R,k}} \quad (13)$$

As shown in (7), $W_{opt,k}$ depends on the channel gains B_k and $1/A_k$, while $W_{E,k}$ is a random variable due to the random property of the transmitted signal S_k and X_k , as shown in (13). Let $\mathbf{W}_{opt} = \{W_{opt,k}\}$, $\mathbf{W}_E = \{W_{E,k}\}$ and $\mathbf{W}_L = \{W_{L,k}\}$ denote the vectors that collect values over all the FFT bins. We perform spectrum analysis on \mathbf{W}_{opt} , \mathbf{W}_L and \mathbf{W}_E by plotting their IFFT spectrum in Fig. 2 for the loopback channel using the ETRI (Electronics and Telecommunications Research Institute) channel model with a maximum delay spread of 30 μs [28]. The D-RFRS has a fixed gain and a delay of 0, while the OTA-RFRS channel has the same delay profile as the loopback channel but independent multipath gains. The FFT size is 8196. Fig. 2-a)~c) are plotted for D-RFRS, and Fig. 2-d)~f) are plotted for OTA-RFRS. The details of the ETRI channel model are presented later in Sec. V-A. Per the simulation parameters listed in Sec. V, this maximum delay spread corresponds to 300 FFT samples. As shown in Fig. 2-a), with D-RFRS, the spectrum of $|IFFT[\mathbf{W}_{opt}]|$ resembles the impulse response of the loopback channel, which has 10 multipath components and maximum delay spread of 300 FFT samples. $|IFFT[\mathbf{W}_E]|$ spreads over the whole spectrum, and $|IFFT[\mathbf{W}_L]|$ is the summation of that of $|IFFT[\mathbf{W}_{opt}]|$ and $|IFFT[\mathbf{W}_E]|$. For OTA-RFRS, similar observation can be found, except that the maximum ‘‘delay spread’’ of $|IFFT[\mathbf{W}_{opt}]|$ is larger than 300 FFT samples as shown in Fig. 2-d).

It is well known in the literature, that DFT windowing can effectively reduce the white noise term [34], [35]. Therefore, a DFT windowing can be applied to the above \mathbf{W}_L to extract \mathbf{W}_{opt} by reducing the error \mathbf{W}_E . An IFFT is first applied to

Fig. 2. Spectrum analysis of the filter weights for D-RFRS: a)~c), and OTA-RFRS: d)~f)

\mathbf{W}_L . The resulting vector $\mathbf{V} = \text{IFFT}[\mathbf{W}_L]$ is then applied with a windowing function as follows:

$$\tilde{V}_k = \begin{cases} V_k, & 0 \leq k < N_L, N_F - N_R + 1 \leq k < N_F \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where $N_W = N_L + N_R$ is the window size. Finally, FFT is applied to the resulting $\tilde{\mathbf{V}} = \{\tilde{V}_k\}$ to obtain the reduced error weights $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_{opt}$. The DFT windowing process is denoted as $\mathcal{D}[\cdot]$.

C. Obtaining the Filter Weights

Notice that the minimum MSE achieving filter weights $W_{L,k}$ can be directly obtained by equating (3) to 0. Therefore, we have

$$W_{L,k} = Y_k / R_k \quad (15)$$

which is referred to as Least Square (LS) estimates.

Based on the insights from the above analysis, in this paper, we propose a novel algorithm to obtain the filter weights. The detailed block diagram of the proposed frequency-domain RF-SIC is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Block diagram of the proposed frequency-domain RF-SIC (expanded block diagram of the RF-SIC block in Fig. 1).

In the proposed frequency-domain RF-SIC, after FFT on the received signals and the RFRS, the LS estimate of the filter weights $W_{L,k}$ are obtained through (15). A DFT windowing is then applied to these LS estimates of the filter weights to reduce the weight error. Therefore, the filter weights become

$$\mathbf{W}_D = \mathcal{D}[\mathbf{W}_L] \quad (16)$$

The resulting filter weights are then applied to the reference signals before being subtracted from the received signals. Finally, for non-OFDM systems, the error signals are converted back to the time domain by IFFT for further processing, while for OFDM systems, the error signals can be passed through directly for further processing.

D. Effect of DFT Windowing

Let $\Delta_{W,k} = W_{D,k} - W_{opt,k}$, substituting (11) into the above (16), we have

$$\{\Delta_{W,k}\} = \mathcal{D}[\mathbf{W}_L] - \mathbf{W}_{opt} = \mathcal{D}[\mathbf{W}_E] \quad (17)$$

where the last equation is assumed that the window size N_W is chosen properly such that $\mathcal{D}[\mathbf{W}_{opt}] = \mathbf{W}_{opt}$.

The MSE of the filter weights, denoted as η , between $W_{D,k}$ and the optimal filter weights $W_{opt,k}$, can be expressed as

$$\eta = \mathcal{E}[\|\Delta_{W,k}\|^2] = \frac{1}{N_F} \mathcal{E}[\|\mathcal{D}[\mathbf{W}_E]\|^2] \quad (18)$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ is the Euclidean norm. The DFT windowing $\mathcal{D}[\cdot]$ can reduce the total MSE with regard to the window size [35], therefore, the MSE of above equation can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \eta &= \frac{N_W}{N_F} \mathcal{E} \left[\left| \frac{(F_k - \sqrt{\rho}W_{opt,k}H_k)S_k + Z_{Y,k} - W_{opt,k}Z_{R,k}}{\sqrt{\rho}H_kS_k + \sqrt{\kappa_R}A_kX_k + Z_{R,k}} \right|^2 \right] \\ &= \frac{N_W[1 + \rho\kappa_Y/\kappa_R + (1 + \kappa_Y/\kappa_R)\sigma^2]}{N_F(\rho + \kappa_R + \sigma^2)} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

In the following, we quantitatively analyze the effect of DFT windowing on the residual SI. Assuming the optimal weights $W_{opt,k}$ in (7) is achieved, Eq. (9) gives the upper bound of the output FWS SINR achieved by the proposed RF-SIC. However, Eq. (9) is a rather loose upper bound since the error in the filter weights results in residual SI. The output signal with residual SI becomes

$$\begin{aligned} E_k &= (F_k - \sqrt{\rho}W_{D,k}H_k)S_k \\ &\quad + (\sqrt{\kappa_Y}B_k - \sqrt{\kappa_R}W_{D,k}A_k)X_k + Z_{E,k} \\ &= (F_k - \sqrt{\rho}W_{D,k}H_k)S_k + \sqrt{\kappa_R}\Delta_{W,k}A_kX_k + Z_{E,k} \\ &= (F_k - \sqrt{\rho}(W_{opt,k} + \Delta_{W,k})H_k)S_k \\ &\quad + \sqrt{\kappa_R}\Delta_{W,k}A_kX_k + Z_{E,k} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where $\sqrt{\kappa_R}\Delta_{W,k}A_kX_k$ is the residual SI term. The desired FWS SINR at the RF-SIC output can then be derived as

$$\begin{aligned} SINR &= \frac{\mathcal{E}[(F_k - \sqrt{\rho}(W_{opt,k} + \Delta_{W,k})H_k)S_k]^2}{\mathcal{E}[\sqrt{\kappa_R}\Delta_{W,k}A_kX_k]^2 + \sigma_{Z_E}^2} \\ &= \frac{1 + \rho(\kappa_Y/\kappa_R + \eta)}{\eta\kappa_R + (1 + \rho\kappa_Y/\kappa_R)\sigma^2} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Substituting (7), (18), and (19) into the above equation and using the fact that $\kappa_R \gg \rho$ and ignoring the noise at high SNR, we arrive at

$$SINR \approx \frac{N_F}{N_W} \quad (22)$$

Note that in [36], an LMS with frequency-domain adaptive filter was proposed for acoustic echo cancellation, where at each iteration, a pair of $2N$ -point IFFT/FFT is applied to

the update coefficients with zeroing the last N FFT bins before the $2N$ -point FFT. This approach is essentially a frequency-domain adaptive filter with a window size N DFT windowing. Subsequently, the filter weights are updated with these update coefficients for the next block of input signals. Applying DFT windowing on the update coefficients improves the LMS convergence rate [36]. In contrast, the approach proposed in this paper only requires one FFT block to achieve the near-optimal filter weights. Moreover, the proposed DFT windowing can be adapted to the channel maximum delay profile to achieve much better performance compared to the fixed window size of half of the FFT size, as shown in the simulation results in Sec. V. Finally, complete insights and analysis on the usage of DFT windowing on the filter weights are offered in this paper.

E. Filter Initialization and Channel Tracking

During the receiver initialization, for the first OFDM symbol or the first block of N_F samples, the filter weights are obtained with the aid of D-RFRS or OTA-RFRS. For static or slow fading channels, the filter weights remain the same and do not need to be updated during the channel coherent time. As the filter weights are obtained with LS estimation and DFT windowing, the required computation complexity is roughly N_F divisions plus $2 N_F$ -point FFT computations ($O(N_F \log N_F)$). With the above computation complexity analysis, the proposed frequency-domain RF-SIC can update the filter weights periodically according to the channel coherent time. Or it can update the filter weights on-the-fly as it offers channel tracking capability with affordable computation complexity.

The proposed frequency-domain RF-SIC smooths the filter weights on the frequency domain relying on the fact that the loopback channels have limited delay spread. Due to the slowly time-varying nature of the loopback channels [33], a time-domain filter can be applied to the filter weights over multiple FFT blocks to further reduce the weight errors.

It is important to note that there is a difference between obtaining filter weights in the proposed frequency-domain RF-SIC and channel estimation in digital baseband cancellation. In RF-SIC, the reference signal is corrupted by the channel, AWGN, nonlinear distortion, and possibly ACI. While in digital baseband cancellation, the feedback symbols for channel estimation are noiseless. Therefore, digital baseband cancellation can obtain channel estimates with much better accuracy, thus can further reduce the residual SI from the output of the RF-SIC [37].

IV. RF-SIC FOR MIMO SYSTEMS

A MIMO system with an IBFD transceiver is illustrated in Fig. 4, where a 2×2 MIMO is depicted as an example. At the IBFD transceiver, the receiver receives the desired signals from the remote transmitter and the SI from its co-located transmitter. Both the remote transmitter and the co-located transmitter are equipped with two transmit antennas. Therefore, the desired signals and the SI signals are the combined signals of multiple transmit antennas through the

forward channels and the loopback channels. In Fig. 4, D-RFRS is depicted as an example of the reference signal for the MIMO RF self-interference cancellation (MIMO-RFSIC).

Fig. 4. Schematic illustration of a MIMO IBFD transceiver.

After FFT, at the k -th FFT bin, let $Y_{i,k}$ denote the received signal at the i -th receive antenna, $F_{ij,k}$ denote the forward channel between the i -th Rx receive antenna and the j -th remote transmit antenna, $B_{ij,k}$ denote the loopback channel between the i -th Rx receive antenna and the j -th co-located transmit antenna, $S_{j,k}$ denote the desired signal transmitted from j -th remote transmit antenna, $X_{j,k}$ denote the SI signal transmitted from j -th co-located transmit antenna, and $Z_{Y,i,k}$ denote the AWGN at the i -th receive antenna, then we have

$$Y_{i,k} = \sum_j F_{ij,k} S_{j,k} + \sqrt{\kappa_Y} \sum_j B_{ij,k} X_{j,k} + Z_{Y,i,k} \quad (23)$$

where κ_Y is the LBS to FWS ratio defined in the previous section. Let $\mathbf{Y}_k = [Y_{1,k}, Y_{2,k}]^T$ denote the received signal in the vector form, then we have

$$\mathbf{Y}_k = \mathbf{F}_k \mathbf{S}_k + \sqrt{\kappa_Y} \mathbf{B}_k \mathbf{X}_k + \mathbf{Z}_{Y,k} \quad (24)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_k = \{F_{ij,k}\}$ is the forward channel matrix, $\mathbf{B}_k = \{B_{ij,k}\}$ is the loopback channel matrix, and \mathbf{S}_k , \mathbf{X}_k , $\mathbf{Z}_{Y,k}$ are the FWS, LBS and AWGN respectively.

Let \mathbf{R}_k denote RF reference signals at the receiver, similar to (24), we have

$$\mathbf{R}_k = \sqrt{\rho} \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{S}_k + \sqrt{\kappa_R} \mathbf{A}_k \mathbf{X}_k + \mathbf{Z}_{R,k} \quad (25)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_k = \{H_{ij,k}\}$ is the channel matrix between the remote transmitter and the RS-Rx, $\mathbf{A}_k = \{A_{ij,k}\}$ is the channel matrix between the co-located transmitter and the RS-Rx, and $\mathbf{Z}_{R,k}$ is the AWGN.

A. A Frequency-Domain MIMO-RFSIC Framework

The frequency-domain RF-SIC designed for SISO can be extended to MIMO in the fashion of SISO replication, as pointed out in [20]. Let \mathbf{W}_k denote the 2×2 filter weights of the proposed frequency-domain MIMO RF-SIC, the error signal can be written as

$$\mathbf{E}_k = \mathbf{Y}_k - \mathbf{W}_k \mathbf{R}_k \quad (26)$$

Substituting (24) and (25) into (26), we have

$$\mathbf{E}_k = (\mathbf{F}_k - \sqrt{\rho}\mathbf{W}_k\mathbf{H}_k)\mathbf{S}_k + (\sqrt{\kappa_Y}\mathbf{B}_k - \sqrt{\kappa_R}\mathbf{W}_k\mathbf{A}_k)\mathbf{X}_k + \mathbf{Z}_{E,k} \quad (27)$$

where $\mathbf{Z}_{E,k} = \mathbf{Z}_{Y,k} - \mathbf{W}_k\mathbf{Z}_{R,k}$.

The goal of SIC is to remove the SI from the received signal, therefore, the optimal filter weights are achieved when the residual SI in the output signal is minimized. The optimization criteria can be written as

$$\mathbf{W}_{opt,k} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{W}} \|(\sqrt{\kappa_Y}\mathbf{B}_k - \sqrt{\kappa_R}\mathbf{W}\mathbf{A}_k)\mathbf{X}_k\|_F^2 \quad (28)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_F$ is the Frobenius norm. Therefore, we arrive at

$$\mathbf{W}_{opt,k} = \sqrt{\kappa_Y/\kappa_R}\mathbf{B}_k\mathbf{A}_k^\dagger/(\mathbf{A}_k^\dagger\mathbf{A}_k) \quad (29)$$

where \dagger is transpose conjugate.

The same design of that in Fig. 3 can be followed here to obtain the filter weights.

B. Low Complexity Frequency-Domain MIMO-RFSIC with D-RFRS

For frequency-domain MIMO-RFSIC with D-RFRS, as illustrated in Fig. 4, examining the reference signal model of (25), $X_{j,k}$ appears individually at the reference signal $R_{j,k}$, $\rho = 0$, and \mathbf{A}_k is a diagonal matrix. With D-RFRS, the optimal filter weights in (29) reduce to

$$W_{opt,i,j,k} = \sqrt{\kappa_Y/\kappa_R}B_{i,j,k}/A_{j,k} \quad (30)$$

Therefore, instead of operating with the matrix form, we propose a low complexity frequency-domain MIMO-RFSIC with D-RFRS that the RF-SIC is performed at each receive antenna chain separately. For a 2×2 MIMO IBFD transceiver with D-RFRS, the frequency-domain MIMO-RFSIC is illustrated in Fig. 5 for the received signal $Y_{1,k}$. Another identical receive chain is implemented for the received signal $Y_{2,k}$.

Fig. 5. Low complexity frequency-domain MIMO-RFSIC for received signal $Y_{1,k}$.

In the following, we use the filter weight $W_{11,k}$ as example to illustrate the process in Fig. 5. The same process is applied to the other filter weights $W_{ij,k}$. The LS estimate, $\hat{W}_{11,k}$, can be written as

$$\hat{W}_{11,k} = Y_{1,k}/R_{1,k} \quad (31)$$

Then DFT windowing is applied to the LS estimates of $\hat{W}_{11,k}$ to arrive at the improved filter weights as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_{11,k} = \mathcal{D}[\hat{\mathbf{W}}_{11,k}] \quad (32)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_{11,k}$ is the vector of $\hat{W}_{11,k}$ at all FFT bins.

Note that in (31), once the filter weight $\tilde{W}_{12,k}$ for signal $X_{2,k}$ is obtained, an improved LS estimate of $\tilde{W}_{11,k}$ can be obtained as

$$\hat{W}_{11,k} = (Y_{1,k} - \tilde{W}_{12,k}R_{2,k})/R_{1,k} \quad (33)$$

Therefore, the filter weights can be estimated in an iterative fashion. The simulation results show that the estimation converges with 3-4 iterations.

In this paper, although we use 2×2 MIMO to illustrate the proposed frequency-domain MIMO-RFSIC algorithms, they can be extended to $N \times N$ MIMO in a straightforward manner.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we provide simulation results to demonstrate the performance of the proposed frequency-domain RF-SIC. In the simulation, the OFDM system uses 8192-point FFT, with a sampling frequency of $64 \cdot 10^6/7$ samples/sec, the sampling duration is about $0.1 \mu\text{s}$. The LBS to FWS power ratio is set to $\kappa_Y = \kappa_R = 30$ dB.

A. Channel Model

In this paper, we consider two loopback channel models used in wireless backhaul where the Rx and Tx can be separated at a larger distance than that of the WiFi transceiver. Since there is in general line-of-sight (LOS) between the co-located Tx and Rx, the loopback channel can be modelled as Rician fading. The first model is a simplified 3-tap model with parameters derived from the channel calculated by ray-tracing for a specific location for IAB [8]. This 3-tap model has maximum delay $7 \mu\text{s}$, with the following power and delay profile [path power (dB)/path delay (μs): [0/0, -25/2, -30/7]. This model is referred to as the IAB model.

The other model is obtained by ETRI Korea from field measurement data with a very large delay spread [28], [33]. Strictly speaking, it is not a general model, rather it is a specific realization of the channel at a location surrounded by many mountains. Nonetheless, it serves as a useful validation of whether the proposed frequency-domain RF-SIC schemes can achieve the required SINR for the desired FWS. The ETRI channel model has the following power and delay profile [path power (dB)/path delay (μs): [0/0, -13/0.3, -25/4, -23/6, -31/8, -26/20, -31/22, 25/24, -33/27, -23/30].

The ETRI channel model has a maximum delay spread, τ_{max} , of $30 \mu\text{s}$, which corresponds to 300 OFDM samples in our simulation parameters.

B. Window Size and Maximum Delay Spread

In Fig. 6, the frequency-domain RF-SIC output FWS SINR is plotted with different window sizes in DFT windowing. It is shown that when using D-RFRS, optimal SINR performance is achieved when the window size is the same as the maximum delay spread, τ_{max} , of the loopback channels. As the window size increases over τ_{max} , the SINR performance decreases. However, performance degradation is small when the window size is slightly larger than τ_{max} .

The proposed frequency-domain RF-SIC is quite robust for slight mismatch between the window size and τ_{max} as long

Fig. 6. The output FWS SINR vs. window size.

as $N_W > \tau_{max}$. In the literature, there are several methods to estimate τ_{max} , e.g. [38] and references therein. If τ_{max} is estimated in baseband processing, it can be fed to the frequency-domain RF-SIC to adjust the window size in the next batch of symbols.

For OTA-RFRS, as shown in Fig. 6, the optimal performance is achieved when the window size is larger than the τ_{max} of the loopback channel. The analysis is presented as follows. In Fig. 6, the reference signal channel A_k is assumed to have the same delay profile as the loopback channel B_k , but with independent multipath gains. As $\kappa_Y = \kappa_R$, the optimal filter weights in (7) become $W_{opt,k} = B_k/A_k$. In Fig. 7, we plot the IFFT of \mathbf{B} , $\{1/A_k\}$ and \mathbf{W}_D using the ETRI channel model with $\tau_{max} = 300$ OFDM samples. Fig. 7-b) shows that the “impulse response” of $\{1/A_k\}$ is much longer than 300 OFDM samples. As multiplication in the frequency domain is convolution in the time domain, the resulting “impulse response” of \mathbf{W}_D , which is a close estimate of \mathbf{W}_{opt} , has a delay spread which is the summation of that of \mathbf{B} and $\{1/A_k\}$. Fig. 7-c) shows that the “impulse response” of \mathbf{W}_D is much larger than the maximum delay spread of the loopback channel.

On the other hand, for D-RFRS, $\{1/A_k\}$ is a flat frequency response, therefore, its “impulse response” only contains one pulse with a very small delay, as shown in Fig. 7-e). Note that for the sake of better illustration, Fig. 7-e) is plotted in linear scale instead of dB scale as in the other sub-plots. In this case, Fig. 7-f) shows the “impulse response” of \mathbf{W}_D has exactly the same maximum delay spread as that of the loopback channel. Therefore, the optimal window size for frequency-domain RF-SIC with D-RFRS is also the same as the maximum delay spread of the loopback channel. As shown in (21), the SINR performance of the frequency-domain RF-SIC is inversely proportional to the window size, the simulation results shown in Fig. 6 agree well with the theory.

Interestingly, although the optimal filter weights for OTA-RFRS have a much larger delay spread than τ_{max} , as in Fig. 7-c) (about 1000 OFDM samples if those “multipath” with power less than -60 dB are ignored), the optimal SINR is achieved at a window size of around 650 OFDM samples

Fig. 7. Illustration of the “impulse response” of the estimated filter weights with OTA-RFRS in a), b), c), and D-RFRS in d), e), f).

in Fig. 6. This is because the larger window size also results in less error reduction in the DFT windowing. As shown in Fig. 7-c), the “multipaths” after delay 650 of OFDM samples have very weak power. Therefore, there is a tradeoff between including more “multipath” for better SI cancellation and less error reduction. The analysis of such trade-off will be presented in a future publication.

C. Effects of ρ

In Fig. 6, the FWS SINR is plotted for the frequency-domain RF-SIC with OTA-RFRS for $\rho = -30, -10$ and 0 dB. The presence of the FWS in the OTA-RFRS serves as additional multipath of FWS. On the other hand, it also increases the MSE of the filter weights as shown in (19). The frequency-domain RF-SIC output FWS SINR is slightly higher when $\rho = 0$ dB compared to smaller ρ . However, the difference between $\rho = -10$ and -30 dB is negligible. As mentioned earlier, ρ is close to $-30 \sim -20$ dB in real systems, therefore, the effect of ρ can be ignored.

D. Effects of Channel Profiles

The FWS SINR for the loopback channel with IAB and ETRI channel models is compared in Fig. 8. As expected, the proposed frequency-domain RF-SIC provides much better FWS SINR performance in the IAB channel, which has a maximum delay spread much smaller than that of the ETRI channel model. Fig. 8 shows that with the ETRI channel model, 44 dB SI cancellation is achieved by the proposed frequency-domain RF-SIC. While for the IAB channel model, 49 dB SI cancellation is achieved.

In Fig. 8, the OTA-RFRS channel profiles are assumed to be the same as that of the SI channels. However, as the RS-Rx is realized with an antenna array pointing directly to the co-located Tx, it is likely that the reference signal channel has a much shorter delay spread than the loopback channel. In Fig. 9, the FWS SINR performance with different OTA-RFRS channel profiles and their corresponding optimal window sizes is plotted for comparison, where the ETRI channel model is

Fig. 8. SINR of FWS after RF cancellation for loopback channel using IAB vs. ETRI channel model, OTA-RFRS (using same channel profile as the loopback channel) and D-RFRS, FWS input SNR=30 dB.

used for the loopback channel. It is shown that the ETRI channel model is the one with the worst performance. The SINR performance with OTA-RFRS and the IAB channel model is close to that of D-RFRS.

Fig. 9. SINR of FWS after RF cancellation for loopback channel using ETRI channel model, and OTA-RFRS using IAB vs. ETRI channel model.

E. SINR vs. MSE of Filter Weights

In Fig. 10, the FWS SINR at the output signal is plotted for frequency-domain RF-SIC at different input SNR values, where SNR is the ratio of the FWS power above the noise floor. The ETRI channel model is used for the loopback channel. Fig. 10 illustrates that the simulation results agree well with the theory in (21) with $\rho = 0$ for D-RFRS. It is worth pointing out that in the simulation, the LBS power is 30 dB above the FWS, or $(30 + SNR)$ dB above the noise floor, therefore, even at a very low SNR region, almost ideal cancellation of LBS can be achieved. As shown in (21) that at a high SNR region the FWS SINR is determined by the MSE of the filter weights, which is determined by the window size of the DFT windowing and FFT size at high SNR. Therefore,

we expect that many methods applied in channel estimation for improved accuracy can be applied to the filter weights estimation in the proposed frequency-domain RF-SIC.

Fig. 10. Comparison of the FWS SINR after RF cancellation with simulation and theory in (21).

F. Frequency-Domain MIMO-RFSIC

For a 2×2 MIMO with D-RFRS, we plot the FWS SINR for the proposed frequency-domain MIMO-RFSIC at different input SNR in Fig. 11. The ETRI channel model is used for the loopback channels in this simulation, and the window size is set to be 300 OFDM samples, the same as the maximum channel delay spread. It is shown in Fig. 11 that the FWS SINR of the proposed frequency-domain MIMO-RFSIC converges with 3 iterations on the filter weights estimation. At high SNR, the FWS SINR converges to 11 dB, which is 3 dB below that of the SISO scenario in Fig. 10. The explanation is that in MIMO-RFSIC, equivalently there are two SI signals from two transmit antennas to be cancelled, therefore, the power of the residual SI is doubled compared to the SISO scenario.

Fig. 11. SINR of FWS for frequency-domain MIMO-RFSIC with D-RFRS.

G. Discussions

As we mentioned earlier that the proposed scheme is different from the digital baseband SIC as it uses an RF reference signal instead of the clean modulated signal. Therefore, the proposed scheme can be applied to both OFDM and non-OFDM systems. Moreover, since the proposed RF-SIC doesn't require demodulating and re-modulating the reference signal, it can easily adapt to work with different broadcasting and broadband communications systems such as ATSC 3.0, DVB-T/T2, WiFi, and 4G/5G.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we proposed a frequency-domain RF self-interference cancellation framework that requires no dedicated training phase and training sequence. The proposed frequency-domain RF-SIC relies on the provided RF reference signal, either in the form of OTA-RFRS or D-RFRS, and a novel algorithm with DFT windowing to obtain the near-optimal filter weights with one FFT block. The obtained filter weights are then applied to the RFRS to reconstruct the SI to be subtracted from the received signal. The proposed frequency-domain RF-SIC has the capability of tracking the channel variation with affordable computation complexity. For MIMO systems, a frequency-domain MIMO-RFSIC framework was proposed as the SISO replication. When D-RFRS is used as the reference signal, a low complexity frequency-domain MIMO-RFSIC was presented. In this paper, we provided insights and theoretic analysis of using DFT windowing to improve the SIC performance. The simulation results agree well with the analysis. The simulation results show that the proposed frequency-domain RF-SIC can achieve 44 dB SI cancellation at moderate SNR when a very challenging channel model with a large delay spread is used for the loopback channel. For a more realistic IAB channel model, 49 dB SI cancellation can be achieved by the proposed frequency-domain RF-SIC.

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